

STUDENT WRITING COMPETENCE IN TERMS OF SELF EFFICACY

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Abstract

This Academic article discusses student writing competence in terms of Self Efficacy in English learning. The purpose of the study was to examine through descriptive quantitative research uses many points of view of self-efficacy in the writing course. The average value of learning outcomes in writing English in a group of students who have high self-efficacy is 79.47 with a standard deviation of 10.85. The average value of learning outcomes in writing English in a group of students who have low self-efficacy is 74.53 with a standard deviation of 8.20. The mode or value that is mostly achieved by students is 80.00. This means that to have writing skills, students must have high self-efficacy. The result shows that the students which have high self-efficacy can produce good writing. Students, who write, need confidence in choosing the topic of writing up to how to express ideas so that the writing produced is interesting to read. This requires confidence in students about their ability to write can produce good writing.

Keywords: Writing Competence, Self efficacy; Learning Outcomes

1. Introduction

Writing seems to be a difficult skill for students to master, especially in Indonesia country as an EFL (English as a Foreign Language). The facts show that many students have difficulty in the learning process or doing assignments related to writing. In this case, the study of writing is still interesting to conduct. This needs to be a concern, considering that writing ability is very important to be mastered by students. According to Muschla (2006), writing is the process to develop their ide and expresses their thoughts as they wish. In brief, writing is an activity to express our ideas in written language. Writing itself has many benefits for students or writers, such as training and enhancing writer creativity, training students to think independently, as a medium to express themselves, improve communication skills, and etc. According to Schwartz (2010: 167), being a writer has many benefits, like make them feel better, happy, relieved after written down, and has positive benefits for the writer. So it is important for them to master it.

Writing is a skill that has a high level of difficulty. According to Petelin (2016: 3), writing is a difficult, complex, time consuming, recursive process. Writing skill itself refers to productive skills that require us to think and express ideas in written form. In writing, many things must be considered. We must have the skills to think creatively to be able to produce good writing. To produce good writing is not always easy even for students with good skills.

Language learning requires an appropriate and effective strategy. A teacher must know and understand various strategies, in language learning to develop teaching skills and also develop learner abilities [1]. With these various strategies it is expected that language learning goals can be achieved. As is known the purpose of learning English is to develop language skills, both verbally and in writing. The language skills in English are the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Good at writing can help them study other skills in English more effectively. Besides that, practicing writing skills will help students get acquainted with new

types of writing as well as consolidate their writing skills. For example, students study writing skills from low to high, [2]. Student difficulties can be found when they have to transfer ideas from Indonesian to English. The second difficulty is that students cannot determine the meaning of words or phrases in writing. Besides, the learning process is still traditional, namely by emphasizing the results of student writing not on the process that should be done. Learning is defined as a deliberate effort by educators to support student learning activities [3]. Learning to write, as well as all three other language skills is a developmental process. In writing learning, intensive practice and practice will help a person become more skilled in writing. Training activities that continue to occur like this allow students to not feel bored in learning to write.

Flower dew [4] mentions several problems when learning to write English for foreign language learners, including the lack of facilities for expressing ideas, taking a long time to write, lack of vocabulary, and the influence of the first language. Truscott [5] asserted that a teacher must be able to provide correct corrections to writing errors, taking into account a number of things such as corrections to be selective and carried out based on learner development, corrections made consistently, and effectively. Nunan [6] argues that learning to write meaningfully is considered the most difficult of other language skills, either as a first language or Mother tongue or as a foreign language. Johnson [7] also states that writing is the most difficult skill for students where English as a second language is difficult to master.

The learning model applied in measuring writing skills has not shown sufficient results in producing graduates who are intelligent and have good competence. This can be measured not only through test results but also through the learning process. Thus, the level of development and progress of students can be known. Difficulties or obstacles experienced by students and the shortcomings possessed by the teachers can be known as the solution to the solution. Seeing the phenomenon above, there needs to be an effort to develop the ability of students to think critically and systematically that must be used well in the learning process in the classroom [8]. According to Gagne quoted by Gredler [9] the process that is important in achieving the learning objectives is to identify internal circumstances and learners. The internal factors of students are self-efficacy or one's belief in one's ability to deal with and solve problems effectively [10]. Students who have high self-efficacy are able to face challenges in attending lectures, do not feel hesitant because they have beliefs that are full of their abilities. Individuals like this according to Bandura [11] will be able to deal with problems and be able to rise from failures that they experience. There are many factors that cause students to have difficulty in writing. Many researchers have carried out studies in this area. Nggawu (2019) investigated one of the students Problems in writing English is their Self Efficacy.

Although some researchers have been conducted to examine self- efficacy as a belief person on the ability in the control of the situation and create something beneficial. Furthermore, It is one and the same as the result of the interaction between the external environment, the mechanism of adjustment, and the ability of personal, experience, and education (Niu 2010). However, Stipek (2001), in Santrock, (2007) explained that self-efficacy is a person who trusts on own merits.

According to Bandura in Schunk (1991:1) Self Efficacy “People judgment of their capacities to organize to organize their capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required to attain designated types of performances”. Generally, according to Jeanne (2011:20) Self Efficacy is a judgment about the ability for doing their performance in to get their goals. Self Efficacy in writing course shows that the students can finish their assignments successfully. As Hodges (2018)) said that the bilingual setting unearthed self-efficacy beliefs to play a significant role in the uptake of language learning.

Self Efficacy gives guidance for students on how to show sense of belonging, thinking, and motivating themselves. In daily life self-efficacy can guide people in facing their problems. According to James L. Gibson, James H. Donnelly, JR, dan John Ivancevich (2012:113) that ‘self -efficacy that one can perform adequately in a situation. Self-efficacy known as the social cognitive theory that individuals can finish the job. The high self-efficacy, so the bigger self- confidence for success. So, a secret condition, someone has low self efficacy tends to give up, while someone with high self- efficacy always thinks for manage the situation. While Steven L. Mc Shane, Marry Ann , Von Glinow (2010:45), ‘self efficacy is a person’s belief that he or she has the ability, motivation, correct role perceptions and favorable situation to complete a task successfully’.. Luthans (2011:203) says that Self efficacy refers to an individual’s condition (or confidence) about his or her abilities to mobilize the motivation, cognitive resource and courses of action needed to successfully execute a specific task within a given context.

So, Self-Efficacy is individual conviction with their ability to get motivation, concept and action were needed for a task for successfully in a certain condition. While Elliot (2005:302) said that every individual belief their abilities in controlling their performance and ability. Karwowski and Kaufman (2017:238) say that Self-efficacy is an individual’s subjective judgment of his/her own ability to be engaged in creative activities.

Annie McKee (2012:82) says that Self Efficacy is someone’s belief that he or she can perform their success in acting, Job, or achieve the goal. While Robert Kreitner, dan Angelo Kinicki (2010:128) say that Self Efficacy as self-confidence in order someone to get a task successfully and believe their ability for finishing the activity. Jennifer M. George, dan Gareth Jones (2012:168) say that Self -efficacy is self- confidence with their ability in finishing their task successfully

Based on the description above, one thing that needs to be considered, especially in learning writing skills, namely self-efficacy. This thing has become important. As one of the language skills that must be possessed, writing is considered a difficult skill compared to other language skills.

2. METHOD OF THE STUDY

This study uses descriptive quantitative According to Siregar (2015) says that describe the object of the research base on the present condition and facts... This type of research involves the description of phenomena in our word. In this type of inquiry, the phenomena described

are basic information, actions, behaviours, and changes of phenomena, but always the description is about what the phenomena look like from the perspective of the researcher or the participants in the research. In most descriptive research studies, instruments must be developed by the researcher due to the fact that the study is related to a specific phenomenon, Lunenburg and Irby (2008). The research variables consist of one dependent variable, the learning outcomes of writing English and one independent variable namely self-efficacy as a moderator variable with the variable self-efficacy consists of high and low self-efficacy.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Description of Learning Outcomes in Writing English in Students with High Self Efficacy

The descriptive analysis of research data about the results of learning English writing students can be seen that the number of students in the group that has high self-efficacy is 31 students. The highest value achieved by students in the group that has high self-efficacy is 95.00 and the lowest value achieved is 59.00. From these data obtained a range of empirical scores, namely the highest difference in value and the lowest value is 36.00, and the theoretical range is 0 to 100. The average value of learning outcomes in writing English in groups of students who have high self-efficacy is 79.47 with standard deviation 10.85. The most reached mode or value by students is 95.00 and the median or middle value of student English writing learning outcomes data after being sorted from the highest to the lowest is 80.00. Data on the results of learning to write English in students in groups that have high self-efficacy are then expressed in frequency distribution. Based on the frequency distribution data presented in table 3.1 below

No	Class Interval	Median	Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	59 – 66	62.5	4	4	13
2	67 – 74	70.5	6	10	19
3	75 – 82	78.5	8	18	26
4	83 – 90	86.5	7	25	23
5	91 – 98	94.5	6	31	19
Total			31		100

It can be seen that as many as 10 of the 31 students (32%) students scored below the average, as many as 8 out of 31 students (26%) obtained scores on the average group and as many as 13 of the 31 students (42%) students obtained the results of learning to write English above average. Furthermore, to clarify the display of learning outcomes in writing English in groups that have high self-efficacy based on the frequency distribution list in each class, it can be presented in the form of a histogram in figure 2 below.

Frequency

Figure 1: Histogram results of learning to write English Students who have high self-efficacy

3.2. Description of Learning Outcomes in Writing English in Students with Low Self Efficacy

The results of the descriptive analysis of research data on the results of learning English writing students can be seen that the number of students in the group that has low self-efficacy is as many as 31 students. The highest value achieved by students in the group that has low self-efficacy is 91.00 and the lowest value achieved is 59.00. From these data obtained a range of empirical scores, namely the difference in the highest value and the lowest value of 32.00, and the theoretical range is 0 to 100. Average value

The results of learning to write English in a group of students who have low self-efficacy is 74.53 with a standard deviation of 8.20. The most reached mode or value by students is 80.00 and the median or middle value of student learning English writing data after being sorted from the highest to the lowest in the group of students who have low self-efficacy is 74.00. Data on the results of learning to write English in students in groups of students who have low self-efficacy are then expressed in the form of frequency distribution. Based on the frequency distribution data presented in table 3.2 below

No	Class Interval	Median	Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	59 – 64	61.5	3	3	10
2	65 – 70	67.5	6	9	19
3	71 – 76	73.5	10	19	32
4	77 – 82	79.5	7	26	23
5	83 – 88	85.5	2	28	6
6	89 – 94	91.5	3	31	10
Total			31		100

It can be seen that in the group of students who have low self-efficacy, as many as 9 out of 31 students (29%) scored below the average, 10 out of 31 students (36%) students obtain scores on the average group and as many as 12 of the 31 students (39%) students get the results of learning to write English above average. Furthermore, to clarify the display of learning outcomes in writing English in groups of students who have low self-efficacy based on the frequency distribution list in each class, it can be presented in the form of a histogram in figure 2 below.

Frequency

Figure 2: Histogram results of learning to write English Students who have low self-efficacy

4. DISCUSSION

The results of calculations with show that the calculated F_{count} for the interaction test between the self-efficacy of students (A) is $F_0(AB) = 49,434$ and F_{table} at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ is $F_{\text{table}}(0.05; 1; 58) = 4.001$. Because $F_{\text{count}} = 49.434 > F_{\text{table}}(0.05; 1; 58) = 4.001$ the conclusions obtained that there is an influence of the interaction between the student's self-efficacy on the results of student English writing. The findings of this study indicate that there is an interaction between the Self Efficacy and the learning outcomes of writing is proven to be true.

According to Saukah [14] writing is one of the language skills that play a very important role. There are several important reasons for teaching writing skills to students, namely for the purposes of strengthening, language development, learning styles, and writing as basic language skills [15]. This means that to have writing skills, students must have high self-efficacy. This is the same as Nggawu [16] emphasizes that the students which have high self-efficacy can produce a good writing. Students, who write, need confidence in choosing the topic of writing up to how to express ideas so that the writing produced is interesting to read. This requires confidence in students about their ability to write in order to produce good writing. This statement is in accordance with the opinion of Kahraman [17], he sees that self-efficacy is one of the influential factors in producing good writing. Confidence in self-efficacy

affects the choices made and actions achieved, because self-efficacy also determines how much effort is made by students, and how long the ability to survive in facing a situation. This is in accordance with what was revealed by Littlejohn, et al. [18] that self-efficacy is influenced by the existence of beliefs to try and be confident in their ability to learn in order to achieve a desired condition. The application of effective learning models can produce higher student grades. Students as unique individuals have different levels of self-efficacy; some have high self-efficacy and low self-efficacy. This condition same with Sharma and George (2015:35) article about Understanding Teacher Self Efficacy require some believe that high self-efficacy to do the most difficult tasks, while others do not this condition requires a situation that is able to accommodate students' self-efficacy levels. To teach students in accordance with the level of self-efficacy they have. It means that in teaching writing course should be paid attention to their self-efficacy level.

5. CONCLUSION

There is a significant effect between Self Efficacy on the results of student learning to write English. There is a significant effect the level of Self Efficacy of students (High Self Efficacy and Low Self Efficacy) on the results of learning English writing for students.

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